

Strengthening Regulatory Compliance and Stakeholder Collaboration for Effective Waste Management in Nigeria

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Abstract:

Waste management has become a significant environmental governance challenge in Nigeria due to rapid urbanisation, population growth, industrial expansion, and changing consumption patterns. Although Nigeria has developed an extensive legal and institutional framework for environmental protection, regulatory compliance in the waste management sector remains weak. This has resulted in persistent environmental pollution, public health concerns, and unsustainable waste disposal practices across many urban centres. This article examines how strengthened regulatory compliance and improved stakeholder collaboration can enhance effective waste management in Nigeria. It analyses the existing legal and institutional framework, with particular emphasis on the regulatory functions of the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA), as well as the roles of state environmental protection agencies and local government authorities. The study adopts a doctrinal research methodology, relying on the analysis of constitutional provisions, environmental legislation, international environmental instruments, and relevant scholarly literature. It is anchored on regulatory compliance theory, stakeholder theory, environmental governance theory, the polluter pays principle, and sustainable development theory. These theoretical perspectives provide a framework for examining the institutional and regulatory factors affecting waste governance in Nigeria. The article identifies several challenges undermining compliance, including weak enforcement capacity, institutional fragmentation, corruption, inadequate funding, and low public awareness. It also highlights the critical roles of stakeholders—such as government institutions, private sector operators, civil society organisations, communities, and the informal waste sector - in strengthening waste governance. Comparative perspectives from jurisdictions including the European Union, the United Kingdom, and South Africa provide useful insights for reform. The study concludes that effective waste management in Nigeria requires stronger regulatory enforcement, improved institutional coordination, and inclusive governance structures that promote stakeholder participation, transparency, and accountability. It recommends strengthening institutional capacity, harmonising regulatory frameworks, encouraging technological innovation, and promoting public–private partnerships.

Keywords: Waste Management, Regulatory Compliance, Environmental Governance, Stakeholder Collaboration, Nigeria.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Consumption patterns have significantly increased the volume and complexity of waste generated across the country. Waste management has consequently emerged as one of the most pressing environmental governance challenges in Nigeria. Rapid urbanisation, population growth, industrial expansion and changing consumption habits have intensified the situation. Major urban centres such as Lagos, Abuja and Port Harcourt continue to grapple with increasing volumes of solid waste, inadequate disposal infrastructure and growing environmental degradation. Inefficient waste collection systems, indiscriminate dumping and weak enforcement of environmental regulations have further heightened public health risks, contributed to flooding and led to the pollution of land and water bodies.¹

The legal and institutional framework for waste management in Nigeria is primarily anchored on the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency Act (NESREA Act), which establishes the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) as the principal federal body responsible for enforcing environmental standards, regulations and compliance.² In addition, state environmental protection agencies and waste management authorities—such as the Lagos State Waste Management Authority (LAWMA)—exercise jurisdiction within their respective states.³ Despite this layered regulatory framework, enforcement remains inconsistent, fragmented and often undermined by institutional overlap, limited funding and weak inter-agency coordination.

Regulatory compliance in environmental law is not merely a function of statutory enactment but of effective monitoring, enforcement and stakeholder engagement. The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended) places environmental protection within the fundamental objectives of state policy, thereby recognising environmental governance as a public duty.⁴ However, constitutional aspirations have not translated into robust compliance culture. Industries, municipal authorities and individuals frequently breach environmental standards with minimal sanctions, thereby weakening deterrence and undermining regulatory credibility.⁵

Equally significant is the limited integration of stakeholders in waste governance. Effective waste management requires coordinated action among government agencies, private sector operators, informal waste collectors, civil society organisations and local communities. Contemporary environmental governance theory emphasises collaborative regulation and shared responsibility as essential to sustainable outcomes.⁶ In Nigeria,

¹. A F Afolabi, 'Municipal Solid Waste Management Challenges in Nigeria' (2015) 7(3) *Journal of Environmental Science and Technology* 145.

². National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (Establishment) Act 2007, s 2.

³. Lagos State Waste Management Authority Law, Cap L73 Laws of Lagos State 2015.

⁴. Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended), s 20.

⁵. O Femi, 'Environmental Compliance and Enforcement in Nigeria: Problems and Prospects' (2018) 12(2) *Nigerian Journal of Environmental Law* 67.

⁶. J Freeman, 'Collaborative Governance in the Administrative State' (1997) 45 *UCLA Law Review* 1.

however, stakeholder collaboration remains largely ad hoc, lacking institutionalised frameworks for participation, transparency and accountability.

The central problem this article addresses is the persistent gap between regulatory design and practical enforcement, compounded by insufficient stakeholder collaboration. While Nigeria possesses a substantial body of environmental legislation, compliance deficits and coordination failures continue to hinder effective waste management. This study therefore examines the regulatory and institutional architecture governing waste management in Nigeria, identifies systemic weaknesses affecting compliance, and proposes strategies for strengthening enforcement mechanisms and multi-stakeholder collaboration.

By situating regulatory compliance within a collaborative governance framework, this article contributes to the growing discourse on environmental sustainability and institutional reform in Nigeria. It argues that strengthening waste management requires not only stricter enforcement but also inclusive governance structures that align regulatory mandates with stakeholder participation and accountability. For clarity and systematic analysis, this article is structured into ten major sections. It begins with the Introduction, followed by conceptual clarifications and the theoretical, legal and institutional framework. The paper then examines the challenges of regulatory compliance in Nigeria.

Subsequent sections explore stakeholder roles in waste management and provide comparative perspectives from other jurisdictions. The discussion then advances to strategies for strengthening regulatory compliance and enhancing stakeholder collaboration. The article concludes with a synthesis of findings and discussion, followed by recommendations and conclusion.

2. CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

For proper analysis of this topic, it is imperative to clarify the core concepts underpinning this study: waste management, regulatory compliance, stakeholder collaboration, and effectiveness within Nigeria's environmental governance framework.

(a) Waste management

This refers to the systematic control of waste generation, collection, segregation, transportation, treatment, recycling, recovery, and final disposal in a manner that safeguards public health and the environment. Under Nigerian law, waste regulation is primarily anchored on the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (Establishment) Act, which establishes the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) and empowers it to enforce

environmental standards and regulations.⁷ Waste management conceptually extends beyond disposal to include waste minimisation and sustainable resource utilisation consistent with environmental protection principles.

(b) Regulatory compliance

This denotes adherence to statutory environmental obligations by individuals, corporations, and public institutions. It encompasses conformity with licensing requirements, environmental impact assessments, monitoring directives, reporting duties, and sanctions prescribed under environmental laws. In Nigeria, compliance mechanisms are reinforced by the Environmental Impact Assessment Act, which mandates environmental assessment for projects likely to significantly affect the environment.⁸ Compliance thus reflects the operationalisation of environmental rule of law in waste governance.

(c) Stakeholder collaboration

It involves coordinated participation among regulatory agencies, state environmental protection authorities, private waste operators, civil society organisations, and local communities. Environmental governance theory recognises that effective waste management cannot rely solely on command-and-control regulation but requires multi-actor cooperation and shared responsibility.⁹ In Nigeria, collaboration is increasingly promoted through public–private partnerships and community-based waste initiatives to address infrastructural and enforcement gaps.

(d) Effective waste management

This implies achieving environmental sustainability, public health protection, and economic efficiency in waste systems. Effectiveness is measured not merely by waste evacuation rates but by compliance levels, reduction in illegal dumping, increased recycling and recovery, and strengthened institutional capacity.¹⁰

Accordingly, conceptual clarification establishes the theoretical and statutory foundation for examining how improved regulatory compliance and enhanced stakeholder collaboration can produce sustainable waste management outcomes in Nigeria.

7. National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (Establishment) Act 2007, ss 1,7 & 8.

8. Environmental Impact Assessment Act, Cap E12, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004, s 2.

9. Philippe Sands and Jacqueline Peel, *Principles of International Environmental Law* (3rd edn, Cambridge University Press 2012) 197–201.

10. A Boyle and C Redgwell, *Birnie, Boyle and Redgwell's International Law and the Environment* (4th edn, Oxford University Press 2021) 268–272.

3. THEORETICAL, LEGAL AND INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK

This study adopts an integrated framework that combines relevant theoretical perspectives with the legal and institutional structures governing waste management. It draws on regulatory compliance theory, stakeholder theory, environmental governance theory, the polluter pays principle, and sustainable development theory to explain how effective waste management depends on both strong regulatory enforcement and inclusive stakeholder participation.

Regulatory compliance theory explains that adherence to environmental laws is influenced not only by enforcement mechanisms such as monitoring and sanctions but also by voluntary compliance, institutional legitimacy, transparency, and incentives.¹¹ This position is reinforced by stakeholder theory, propounded by R. Edward Freeman, which emphasises that effective governance requires balancing the interests of all stakeholders, including regulators, private sector actors, communities, and informal waste participants.¹² In the same vein, environmental governance theory advocates a shift from a purely state-centric approach to a multi-level, collaborative system involving federal, state, and local institutions, thereby addressing fragmentation and coordination challenges within Nigeria's waste management framework.¹³

These perspectives are further strengthened by the polluter pays principle, which imposes financial responsibility for environmental harm on the polluter, thereby promoting accountability and deterrence.¹⁴ Complementarily, sustainable development theory provides a normative framework that integrates environmental protection with economic growth and social inclusion, ensuring that waste management policies are both efficient and equitable.¹⁵

Legally, waste management in Nigeria is anchored on constitutional and statutory provisions. Section 20 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended) imposes a duty on the State to protect and improve the environment.¹⁶ The National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (Establishment) Act 2007 establishes the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency and empowers it to enforce environmental standards, conduct inspections, and impose sanctions for non-compliance.¹⁷ In addition, the Environmental Impact Assessment Act 2004 mandates prior environmental assessment

¹¹. Ayodele Oni, 'Environmental Regulation and Compliance in Nigeria' (2019) 7 *Nigerian Journal of Environmental Law* 45.

¹². R Edward Freeman, *Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach* (Pitman 1984).

¹³. J N Rosenau, 'Governance in the Twenty-First Century' (1995) 1 *Global Governance* 13.

¹⁴. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), *The Polluter Pays Principle: Definition, Analysis and Implementation* (OECD 1975).

¹⁵. United Nations, *Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development: Our Common Future* (1987).

¹⁶. Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended), s 20.

¹⁷. National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (Establishment) Act 2007, ss 7-8.

for projects likely to have significant environmental effects, including waste-related activities, thereby strengthening preventive regulation.¹⁸

Institutionally, waste management in Nigeria operates within a multi-tiered governance structure involving federal agencies such as NESREA, state environmental protection agencies, and local government councils responsible for waste collection and sanitation services. This structure reflects the principles of environmental governance but also necessitates effective coordination to avoid regulatory overlap and enforcement gaps.¹⁹

At the international level, several frameworks provide guiding standards for sustainable waste management. The Basel Convention on the Control of Transboundary Movements of Hazardous Wastes and Their Disposal regulates the transboundary movement of hazardous waste and promotes environmentally sound disposal practices.²⁰ The United Nations Environment Programme, through initiatives such as the Global Waste Management Outlook, supports integrated waste management strategies.²¹ Similarly, the World Bank report *What a Waste 2.0* highlights the need for policy reforms, private sector participation, and technological innovation in waste management.²² Furthermore, the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, particularly Goals 11 and 12, emphasise sustainable cities and responsible consumption and production.²³ The circular economy model, widely adopted in jurisdictions such as the European Union, also promotes waste reduction through reuse, recycling, and resource recovery.²⁴

Overall, this integrated framework demonstrates that effective waste management in Nigeria depends on the synergy between sound legal instruments, functional institutions, and participatory governance. While the existing framework is robust, its effectiveness ultimately hinges on improved enforcement, stronger inter-agency collaboration, and sustained stakeholder engagement.

4. CHALLENGES OF REGULATORY COMPLIANCE IN NIGERIA

Despite the existence of a comprehensive legal and institutional framework, regulatory compliance in waste management in Nigeria faces significant structural and operational challenges. These challenges undermine enforcement effectiveness and limit the achievement of sustainable waste governance.

¹⁸. Environmental Impact Assessment Act 2004.

¹⁹. Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended), Fourth Schedule.

²⁰. Basel Convention on the Control of Transboundary Movements of Hazardous Wastes and Their Disposal.

²¹. United Nations Environment Programme, *Global Waste Management Outlook* (2015).

²². World Bank, *What a Waste 2.0: A Global Snapshot of Solid Waste Management to 2050* (2018).

²³. United Nations, *Sustainable Development Goals* (2015).

²⁴. European Commission, *Circular Economy Action Plan* (2020).

(a) Institutional weakness and limited enforcement capacity

One major challenge is institutional weakness and limited enforcement capacity. Although the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) is empowered under the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (Establishment) Act to enforce environmental standards, practical enforcement is often constrained by inadequate funding, shortage of trained personnel, insufficient monitoring equipment, and limited logistical support.²⁵ These deficiencies reduce the frequency of inspections and weaken deterrence against regulatory violations.

Another significant challenge is regulatory overlap and jurisdictional fragmentation. Nigeria's federal structure distributes environmental responsibilities among federal, state, and local authorities. While section 20 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 provides a constitutional basis for environmental protection,²⁶ overlapping mandates between federal agencies and state environmental protection bodies often create uncertainty, duplication of functions, and weak inter-agency coordination.²⁷ This fragmentation hampers uniform compliance enforcement across jurisdictions.

(b) Low compliance culture and weak deterrence mechanisms

Low compliance culture and weak deterrence mechanisms also contribute to persistent violations. In many instances, industries and waste operators perceive enforcement as inconsistent, and penalties may not be sufficiently dissuasive to prevent infractions. Regulatory theory suggests that when monitoring is irregular and sanctions are weak, regulated entities are less likely to comply voluntarily.²⁸

(c) Corruption and administrative inefficiencies

Also, corruption and administrative inefficiencies pose serious barriers to effective compliance. Discretionary enforcement powers may be compromised by informal practices, political interference, or lack of transparency in regulatory processes.²⁹ Such systemic issues undermine public confidence and weaken the legitimacy of environmental institutions.

²⁵. National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (Establishment) Act 2007, ss 7–8.

²⁶. Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended), s 20.

²⁷. O Adewale, 'Environmental Regulation and Enforcement in Nigeria' (2009) 1(1) *Nigerian Journal of Environmental Law* 45, 52–54.

²⁸. Neil Gunningham and Peter Grabosky, *Smart Regulation: Designing Environmental Policy* (Clarendon Press 1998) 37–41.

²⁹. A Adebayo, 'Corruption and Environmental Governance in Nigeria' (2012) 6(3) *African Journal of Legal Studies* 211, 218–220.

(d) Informal nature of waste management operations

Another challenge is the informal nature of waste management operations, particularly in urban centres. A significant portion of waste collection and recycling activities is carried out by informal actors who operate outside formal regulatory frameworks. Their exclusion from official regulatory systems makes monitoring and compliance enforcement difficult.

(e) Low public awareness and limited stakeholders' engagement

Finally, low public awareness and limited stakeholder engagement impede compliance. Effective waste management requires active participation from households, communities, and private operators. Where awareness of environmental obligations is weak, regulatory compliance becomes difficult to sustain.³⁰

Addressing these challenges requires strengthening institutional capacity, clarifying regulatory mandates, enhancing inter-agency collaboration, improving transparency, formalising informal sector participation, and adopting participatory compliance strategies. Without confronting these structural impediments, efforts to strengthen regulatory compliance and stakeholder collaboration for effective waste management in Nigeria may remain inadequate.

5. STAKEHOLDERS ROLES IN WASTE MANAGEMENT

Effective waste management in Nigeria is anchored on the coordinated participation of multiple stakeholders within an established legal and institutional framework. Regulatory compliance and sustainable environmental governance cannot be achieved solely through state enforcement; rather, they depend on shared responsibility among government institutions, private actors, communities, and civil society.

At the federal level, the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) serves as the principal regulatory authority, empowered to set environmental standards, monitor compliance, conduct inspections, and prosecute offenders.³¹ Complementing this role, State Governments and their Environmental Protection Agencies or Waste Management Authorities oversee the operational aspects of waste management, including collection, transportation, landfill administration, and enforcement of sanitation laws within their jurisdictions, in line with constitutional responsibilities.³² Local Government Councils further reinforce compliance at the grassroots through waste evacuation, public health monitoring, and enforcement of sanitation by-laws, as recognised under the Fourth Schedule to the Constitution.³³

³⁰. Philippe Sands and Jacqueline Peel, *Principles of International Environmental Law* (3rd edn, Cambridge University Press 2012) 197–199

³¹. National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (Establishment) Act 2007, ss 7–8.

³². Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended), Second Schedule, Part II.

³³. *Ibid*, Fourth Schedule.

Beyond governmental actors, the private sector plays a vital role through service delivery, recycling initiatives, and waste treatment operations, often facilitated by public–private partnerships, while remaining subject to licensing requirements and environmental standards.³⁴ Communities and households, as primary waste generators, are central to achieving compliance through responsible consumption, waste segregation, and proper disposal practices.³⁵ Civil society organisations also contribute significantly by promoting environmental awareness, monitoring regulatory performance, and enhancing transparency and accountability in governance processes.³⁶

In addition, the informal waste sector—comprising waste pickers and recyclers—provides substantial support to material recovery and recycling efforts. Although largely unregulated, its integration into formal waste management systems offers opportunities to improve efficiency, strengthen compliance, and advance socio-economic inclusion.³⁷

Overall, stakeholders’ roles in waste management are complementary and interdependent. Strengthening regulatory compliance in Nigeria therefore requires a collaborative governance approach that integrates enforcement with active stakeholder participation, shared accountability, and institutional synergy.³⁸

6. COMPARATIVE PERSPECTIVES

A comparative analysis of waste management frameworks in other jurisdictions provides valuable insights for strengthening regulatory compliance and stakeholder collaboration in Nigeria. Examining international best practices reveals innovative enforcement mechanisms, institutional coordination models, and participatory governance structures that can inform reforms within Nigeria’s environmental regulatory regime.

(i) European Union

The European Union has developed a comprehensive waste governance framework anchored on the Waste Framework Directive 2008/98/EC. The Directive establishes the waste hierarchy—prioritising prevention, reuse, recycling, recovery, and disposal—and imposes binding obligations on Member States to implement extended producer responsibility (EPR) schemes and national waste management plans.³⁹ Compliance is reinforced through monitoring, reporting obligations, and judicial oversight by

³⁴. O. Fagbohun, *Environmental Law in Nigeria* (Lagos: Princeton Publishing, 2010) 412.

³⁵. United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), *Waste Management Outlook for Africa* (2018) 56.

³⁶. J. A. Omotola, ‘Civil Society and Environmental Governance in Nigeria’ (2014) 6 *Journal of Sustainable Development* 45.

³⁷. World Bank, *What a Waste 2.0: A Global Snapshot of Solid Waste Management to 2050* (2018) 103.

³⁸. A. Jordan et al, ‘Environmental Governance and Stakeholder Participation’ (2015) 24 *Environmental Politics*

1.

³⁹. Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on Waste [2008] OJ L312/3, arts 4–8.

supranational institutions. The EU model demonstrates the effectiveness of harmonised standards, strong enforcement mechanisms, and structured stakeholder involvement in achieving high recycling rates and environmental protection.

(ii) United Kingdom

In the United Kingdom, regulatory enforcement combines statutory obligations with economic instruments such as landfill taxes and producer responsibility schemes. The Environmental Protection Act 1990 establishes duties of care for waste producers and empowers regulators to impose penalties for non-compliance.⁴⁰ The integration of fiscal incentives with enforcement mechanisms has significantly reduced landfill dependence and promoted recycling initiatives.

(iii) South Africa

Similarly, in the South Africa, the National Environmental Management: Waste Act 2008 provides a structured framework for cooperative environmental governance.⁴¹ The Act promotes integrated waste management plans, licensing requirements, and extended producer responsibility schemes, while emphasising coordination among national, provincial, and municipal authorities. South Africa's approach is particularly instructive for Nigeria, given comparable socio-economic and institutional challenges within a federal or quasi-federal governance structure.

Comparatively, these jurisdictions demonstrate key elements necessary for effective waste governance: clear legislative mandates, strong enforcement institutions, economic incentives for compliance, formal integration of the informal sector, and institutionalised stakeholder participation.⁴²

For Nigeria, adapting such comparative lessons would involve strengthening enforcement capacity under the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (Establishment) Act, institutionalising extended producer responsibility frameworks, enhancing inter-governmental coordination, and embedding economic instruments alongside traditional command-and-control regulation.

Thus, comparative perspectives underscore that effective waste management is achieved not merely through the existence of laws, but through robust compliance systems, stakeholder collaboration, and adaptive governance models capable of responding to evolving environmental challenges.

⁴⁰. Environmental Protection Act 1990 (UK), ss 33–34.

⁴¹. National Environmental Management: Waste Act 2008 (South Africa), ss 11–28.

⁴². Philippe Sands and Jacqueline Peel, *Principles of International Environmental Law* (3rd edn, Cambridge University Press 2012) 197–205.

7. STRATEGIES FOR STRENGTHENING REGULATORY COMPLIANCE AND ENHANCING

Effective waste management in Nigeria requires not only a sound legal framework but also coordinated, institutionalised collaboration among key stakeholders. While existing environmental laws and regulations provide a foundation for compliance, enforcement gaps, weak institutional capacity, overlapping mandates, and low public awareness continue to undermine their effectiveness. Accordingly, strengthening regulatory compliance must proceed alongside enhanced stakeholder collaboration within a unified governance framework.⁴³

A central strategy is institutional capacity building and coordination. Regulatory agencies such as the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) and State Environmental Protection Agencies must be adequately funded, staffed, and equipped with modern enforcement tools, including digital monitoring systems and laboratory facilities. Strengthening institutional autonomy and reducing political interference will improve enforcement outcomes. At the same time, harmonisation of federal and state regulatory frameworks, coupled with clear delineation of responsibilities, joint task forces, and inter-agency data sharing, is essential to eliminate duplication, reduce regulatory conflicts, and promote uniform compliance standards nationwide.⁴⁴

Closely linked to this is the adoption of technology-driven and data-based enforcement mechanisms. Electronic tracking of waste streams, geospatial monitoring, and digital reporting platforms enhance transparency, enable risk-based inspections, and improve accountability. These mechanisms are further strengthened where enforcement is supported by effective sanction and incentive systems, including consistent application of administrative fines, closure orders, and criminal penalties, alongside positive incentives such as tax rebates, compliance certifications, and public recognition schemes to encourage voluntary compliance.⁴⁵

Equally important is the role of public–private partnerships (PPPs) and market-based collaboration. The participation of private waste operators, recyclers, and investors brings technical expertise and financial capacity necessary for efficient waste service delivery. Regulatory frameworks must therefore ensure transparent licensing, performance benchmarks, and compliance audits, while integrating incentive-based

⁴³. See generally National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (Establishment) Act

2007; Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended).

⁴⁴. Ibid; also see A. Boyle and C. Redgwell, *Birnie, Boyle and Redgwell's International Law and the Environment*

(4th edn, OUP 2021).

⁴⁵. OECD, *Regulatory Enforcement and Inspections Toolkit* (OECD 2018).

instruments such as Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) schemes, which impose lifecycle responsibility on producers for post-consumer waste.⁴⁶

At the grassroots level, community participation and civil society engagement are indispensable. Public awareness campaigns, community-based monitoring, and accessible reporting mechanisms empower citizens to report environmental violations and enhance accountability. The integration of informal waste pickers into formal systems, alongside the involvement of traditional institutions, strengthens traceability and fosters a culture of compliance. Civil society organisations further reinforce this framework through advocacy, public interest litigation, and policy engagement, thereby bridging accountability gaps and promoting transparency.⁴⁷

In addition, judicial support and international collaboration play a complementary role. The designation of specialised environmental courts or trained judicial officers can expedite enforcement and ensure consistent interpretation of environmental laws. Nigeria may also benefit from international partnerships, which provide opportunities for capacity building, technology transfer, and adoption of best practices in circular economy and sustainable waste governance.⁴⁸

In sum, regulatory compliance and stakeholder collaboration are mutually reinforcing pillars of effective waste management. An integrated approach that combines institutional strengthening, coordinated governance, technological innovation, stakeholder participation, and enforceable accountability mechanisms is essential for achieving a sustainable and compliance-driven waste management system in Nigeria.

8. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The review of recent empirical and policy literature on waste management in Nigeria reveals several key patterns regarding regulatory compliance and stakeholder collaboration. For enhance deliberation, we shall discuss this under two sub-heads: findings and discussions.

(A) FINDINGS

(i) Regulatory frameworks exist but are weakly implemented

Many national and subnational regulations governing solid and hazardous waste management have been developed (e.g., NESREA Act and sanitation laws) but their enforcement remains inconsistent and weak due to insufficient funding, administrative capacity, and poor coordination among agencies. This gap contributes to continued non-

⁴⁶. National Environmental (Extended Producer Responsibility) Regulations 2014; NESREA Guidelines on EPR.

⁴⁷. Environmental Impact Assessment Act Cap E12 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004; J. Razzaque, *Environmental Governance in Africa* (Routledge 2019).

⁴⁸. United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), *Global Waste Management Outlook* (UNEP 2015); Rio Declaration on Environment and Development 1992.

compliance by households and businesses, which in turn perpetuates illegal dumping, open burning, and environmental degradation.⁴⁹

(ii) Fragmented mandates lead to institutional inefficiencies

Studies consistently highlight that fragmented institutional responsibilities among federal, state, and local governments weaken enforcement and accountability. Local governments, constitutionally responsible for waste collection, often lack the infrastructure and personnel needed for effective service delivery. Fragmentation also leads to overlapping mandates and poor coordination, undermining regulatory compliance across jurisdictions.⁵⁰

(iv) Stakeholder collaboration improves governance outcomes

Empirical findings demonstrate that collaboration among government agencies, private sector actors, community groups, and informal waste workers significantly enhances waste governance outcomes. Collaboration is positively associated with improved policy implementation, resource mobilisation, and compliance behaviours among residents. For example, multi-actor partnerships help bridge gaps in service delivery, increase awareness of sanitation laws, and create accountability mechanisms that support regulation.⁵¹

(v) Public awareness and participation are critical

Several case studies show that public awareness and participation influence compliance with sanitation regulations. In urban centres such as Akure and Owo, residents' perceptions of environmental laws and willingness to participate in sanitation activities are shaped by their understanding of the associated health and environmental benefits. Without strong public engagement, regulatory policies are less likely to translate into improved practices on the ground.⁵²

(v) Technological and innovation barriers restrict progress

While innovations such as GIS mapping, mobile applications for waste collection coordination, and digital monitoring systems can support compliance and reporting, their

⁴⁹. Nigeria's solid waste management regulatory frameworks are often poorly enforced due to capacity and coordination challenges, resulting in pervasive non-compliance and environmental harm.

⁵⁰. Collaboration between government agencies, CBOs, private waste managers, and communities enhances waste governance outcomes and compliance with sanitation policies.

⁵¹. Collaboration between government agencies, CBOs, private waste managers, and communities enhances waste governance outcomes and compliance with sanitation policies;

Technological innovations such as GIS mapping and mobile waste apps can support compliance but are hindered by cost and limited capacity; and Stakeholder forums and policy dialogues reinforce collaborative approaches in construction and industrial waste management, bridging policy and practice.

⁵². Public perception studies in Nigerian cities show that awareness of environmental sanitation laws influences compliance and participation in waste management initiatives.

adoption in Nigeria is limited by cost, technical capacity, and infrastructure constraints. These barriers reduce the potential impact of regulatory monitoring and stakeholder communication platforms.⁵³

(vi) Collaborative policy revisions strengthen compliance prospects

There is evidence that structured stakeholder dialogues to review and update environmental regulations—bringing together public authorities and private organisations—can strengthen policy relevance and alignment with international best practices. These engagements also help build ownership of compliance goals among diverse actors, which is critical for long-term sustainable waste governance.⁵⁴

(B) DISCUSSION

Overall, the findings suggest that strengthening regulatory compliance in Nigeria requires a dual focus: improving the enforcement capacity of existing legal frameworks while fostering inclusive, sustained collaboration among stakeholders at all levels. Simply having laws in place is not sufficient; implementation gaps must be bridged through institutional coordination, participatory mechanisms, and resource investments that support monitoring, awareness, and service delivery.

Stronger collaboration contributes to better compliance in several ways including enhancement of information flows between authorities and communities, leading to clearer expectations and shared accountability.⁵⁵ Furthermore, this leverages the capacities of non-state actors (e.g., NGOs, private waste companies) to fill operational gaps, especially in areas where government services are limited.⁵⁶ It also strengthens public trust and civic engagement, which has been shown to correlate with greater adherence to sanitation norms and environmental regulations.⁵⁷ Thus, the effective integration of regulatory compliance and stakeholder collaboration forms a synergistic basis for improving waste management outcomes across Nigeria’s urban and peri-urban environments.

⁵³. Technological innovations such as GIS mapping and mobile waste apps can support compliance but are hindered by cost and limited capacity.

⁵⁴. Stakeholder forums and policy dialogues reinforce collaborative approaches in construction and industrial waste management, bridging policy and practice.

⁵⁵. Collaboration between government agencies, CBOs, private waste managers, and communities enhances waste governance outcomes and compliance with sanitation policies.

⁵⁶. Technological innovations such as GIS mapping and mobile waste apps can support compliance but are hindered by cost and limited capacity.

⁵⁷. Public perception studies in Nigerian cities show that awareness of environmental sanitation laws influences compliance and participation in waste management initiatives.

9. RECOMMENDATIONS

In order to strengthen regulatory compliance and enhance stakeholder collaboration for effective waste management in Nigeria, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Regulatory bodies responsible for environmental protection should be adequately funded, staffed, and equipped to enforce waste management regulations effectively. Agencies such as the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) and state environmental protection agencies should be empowered to monitor compliance, conduct inspections, and impose sanctions on violators. Improved institutional capacity will enhance regulatory enforcement and deter environmental infractions.⁵⁸
2. Effective waste management requires active collaboration among government agencies, private waste operators, community organizations, and civil society groups. The government should encourage public-private partnerships (PPPs) in waste collection, recycling, and disposal services. Such collaborative arrangements can improve efficiency, promote innovation, and ensure broader participation in environmental management.⁵⁹
3. There should be sustained public enlightenment campaigns on the importance of proper waste disposal and environmental sanitation. Environmental education programs should be integrated into school curricula and community outreach initiatives. Increased awareness will encourage responsible waste disposal practices among citizens and foster a culture of environmental responsibility.⁶⁰
4. Government policies should encourage recycling and resource recovery through incentives such as tax reliefs, grants, and subsidies for recycling companies. Establishing recycling facilities and promoting waste-to-energy initiatives can significantly reduce the volume of waste disposed in landfills while creating economic opportunities.⁶¹
5. Existing environmental laws and regulations should be periodically reviewed and updated to reflect emerging waste management challenges. Clear enforcement mechanisms and stricter penalties for non-compliance should be incorporated to ensure that individuals and corporations adhere to waste management standards⁶².

⁵⁸. Environmental Impact Assessment Act, Cap E12 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria (LFN) 2004; see also National Environmental (Sanitation and Waste Control) Regulations 2009.

⁵⁹. A. O. Fagbohun, *Environmental Law and Practice in Nigeria* (Lagos: Law Press Ltd., 2010) 214.

⁶⁰. O. F. Oloruntoba and A. A. Adewole, 'Waste Management and Environmental Sustainability in Nigeria' (2018) 12 *Nigerian Journal of Environmental Law* 45.

⁶¹. A. M. Agunwamba, 'Solid Waste Management in Nigeria: Problems and Issues' (2003) 22(6) *Environmental Management* 849.

⁶². National Environmental (Sanitation and Waste Control) Regulations 2009.

6. Local communities should be actively involved in waste management planning and implementation. Community-based waste management initiatives, including neighborhood sanitation programs and waste sorting schemes, can significantly improve compliance and sustainability.⁶³

10. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, strengthening regulatory compliance and promoting robust stakeholder collaboration are indispensable for addressing the persistent waste management challenges in Nigeria. Through improved institutional capacity, enhanced legal frameworks, community participation, and innovative waste management practices, Nigeria can move toward a more sustainable and environmentally responsible waste management system.

⁶³. U. O. Aina, 'Community Participation in Environmental Management in Nigeria' (2016) 8 *Journal of Sustainable Development Law and Policy* 132.